

Spatial and Temporal Pattern of Migration in India between first two censuses of 21st century

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Abstract

Migration is the most important component out of the three components of population change and most helpful to understand regional elements of demographic studies. Migration makes the distribution of population on earth more meaningful. Therefore this paper is presented to represent spatial pattern and inter-state migration in India and to calculate state and sex wise variation in in-migration and out-migration across India. Present paper is based on census migration data of 2001 and 2011. In the presented paper, in-migration rate, out-migration rate, and variation in migration have been computed separately for both males and females. Simple percent distribution method is used to pattern of inter-state and intra-state migration across India. When we look at results, In-migration and out-migration have uneven pattern because more than half of total in-migrants and out-migrants clustered in 5 to 6 states only where urbanization and industrial growth is maximum and remains of the total migrants are spreader across other India. In 2001, migration was male dominated but in 2011, the picture is opposite and the migration became female dominated.

Keywords; Migration, In-migration, Out-migration, spatial pattern, Census.

Introduction

Migration is one of the most important phenomena after fertility and mortality, which impact the population change in a country or a state. The movement of peoples from their home place to another place in order to live and work is known as migration. Lee (1966, p.49) broadly considers migration as a permanent or semi-permanent change of residence with no restrictions on the distance involved in the movement. Relocation of peoples within a nation is called internal migration. In internal migration population does not cross the political boundaries of its nation. Rather, it moves from the place of origin to another convenient place.

Internal migration is primarily the result of internal disparities of economic standards, physical and social conditions of a country. The movement of peoples from one state to another state is known as inter-state migration. But when the peoples moves from one district to another by covering a short distance then it is known as local migration. On the basis of direction of migration internal migration is classified in the following four classes.

- 1) Rural to Urban Migration
- 2) Urban to Urban Migration
- 3) Rural to Rural Migration
- 4) Urban to Rural Migration

In India, Rural to Urban migration and Rural to Rural migration are most trending at all time. Rural to Urban migration is done by young population of the country in search of employment and better life. India is country of villages and agriculture is the primary occupation of the peoples in villages, so Rural to Rural migration is done by the girls after marriage and by farmers in respect to marginal lands for agriculture like urbanization, both of push and pull factors generate the migratory tendencies among the people. Push factors are poverty, lack of education, socio-cultural and health care facilities, unemployment and lack of banking and insurance services that are found in villages in India. Pull factors are better employment opportunities, better education and health care facilities, better socio-cultural environment and freedom from cast and religion system. Migration is continuously increasing at the fast rate in India after independence that leads to growth of urbanization. So, migration and urbanization are closely interrelated to each other. Increase in migration and urbanization also generate some problems like pollution, imbalance in distribution and density of population, extra pressure on natural resources of a specific place and on another place from where the peoples migrate, the imbalance is established between natural and human resources. Hence, it can be said that both urbanization and migration produce positive results as well as negative results.

All those persons who have migrated from their previous place of residence to another new place between 2001 and 2011 are considered as migrants. This term migration include all persons who has migrated at any time between these two census years is considered to be a migrant whether he migrated in 2001-2002 or 10 days before the census of 2011. In this analysis the two rates, which are related to migration itself, have also been calculated and are known as in-migration and out-migration. These both rates have been calculated separately for male and females.

In-migration rate may be defined as the number of persons enumerated in the destination place, or state, who have come from the other places or states of the same country, per hundred enumerated population of the destination place or state.

Study Area:

India is an Asian country located in south Asia extends between latitudes 8°4'N and. 37°6'N and longitudes 68°7'E and 97°25'E. It is the 7th biggest country in size and 2nd largest country in population in the world. India got freedom from British rule in 1947 and get divided in two different nations namely India and Pakistan. After Independence, India made many historical records in various fields such that agriculture, science and technology, space, sports and research. Author studies in the present paper the spatial pattern of internal migration in India and the sex wise variation in In-migration and out-migration during the last two censuses.

Objectives:

The present paper has the following objectives:

- 1) To examine the spatial and temporal pattern of internal migration in India.
- 2) To study the sex wise variation in In-migration and out-migration during the last two censuses of 2001 and 2011.

Database and Methodology:-

Volume of in-migration to the state

$$\text{In-migration rate} = \frac{\text{Volume of in-migration to the state}}{\text{Total enumerated mid-year population of the state}} * 100$$

Out-migration rate may be defined as the number of persons who have migrated out of the place or state to other place or state of the country, per hundred enumerated population of the origin place or state.

Volume of out-migration to the state

$$\text{Out-migration rate} = \frac{\text{Volume of out-migration to the state}}{\text{Total enumerated mid-year population of the state}} * 100$$

Pattern of inter-state migration is described by using simple percent distribution.

Migration variables: a) Volume of migration, b) Rate of migration, c) Share of the states total migration to country's total migration.

Result and Discussion:-**Pattern of Migration****In-migration:**

Table 1, 2 and 3 represents the state wise rate and share of total and sex wise In-migration in states from other states in India between 2001 & 2011. Total 21,113,870 peoples migrated on interstate level in India between 2001 and 2011 in all 35 states and union territories out of which 10040966 are male and 11,072,904 are females. Sex ratio among In-migrants comes to 110 females per 100 males. Thus, inter-state migration is more female selective. Thus the data indicates predominance of female mobility over male mobility in India. High rate of total and male inter-state migration seems in Daman & Diu and Dadra & Nagar Haveli followed by Chandigarh and New Delhi union territories. In states, the states having a small geographical area like Goa, Haryana, Uttrakhand, Punjab and Himachal Pradesh etc. have the higher rate of inter-state migration whereas the states having larger geographic area like Maharashtra, Karnataka, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh etc. have the low rate of Inter-state In-migration. Only 5 states viz. Maharashtra, Karnataka, Gujarat, NCT of Delhi, and Uttar Pradesh consist more than half 51 percent share of total interstate In-migrants within the country. Main reason for this heavy migration in these 5 states from other states are better employment opportunities, better education and better living standards etc. in the metropolitan cities and other big cities i.e. Mumbai, Pune, Nagpur, Nashik, Delhi, Noida, Greater Noida, Ghaziabad, Kanpur, Agra, Prayagraj, Varanasi, Bengaluru, Mysore, Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Surat etc. Some union territories i.e. Daman and Diu, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Lakshadweep, and Andaman and Nicobar etc. have very less percentage of total inter-state migrants because of no economic or industrial development in these union territories. In male In-migration states i.e. Goa, Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, followed by Maharashtra, Gujarat, Uttrakhand, Haryana, Punjab and Himachal Pradesh etc. have the higher rate of male In-migration in respect of their total male population. Half of the total male In-migrants are found in only 5 states viz. Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka, Haryana and Punjab etc. Delhi is the single union territory having higher share of male In-migrants. More employment in the field of agriculture and manufacturing industries, better living and educational standards are the point of attraction of male In-migrants in these states. All union territories experience higher rate of female in-migration excepting Lakshadweep but all union territories experience higher rate of female In-migration than national average. Total 13 states experiencing lower rate of female In-migration than national average. The states of Haryana and Goa having higher rate of female In-migration. Some of the states viz. Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, Punjab, Himachal Pradesh, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Maharashtra and Karnataka experience moderate and higher female In-migration than the national average.

Table 1: Rate and share of In-migration and Out-migration in India between 2001 and 2011.

Sr. No.	States	Total in-migrants from other states	Total Out-migrants to other states	Total Population	Rate of In-migration	Share of total In-migrants	Rate of Out-migration	Share of total Out-migrants
1	Jammu & Kashmir	70,628	118,532	12,541,302	0.57	0.33	0.95	0.56
2	Himachal Pradesh	205,896	171,783	6,864,602	3	0.98	1.8	2.37
3	Punjab	986,509	500,897	27,743,338	3.56	4.67	2.5	0.81
4	Chandigarh	242,517	125,341	1,055,450	22.98	1.15	11.88	0.59
5	Uttarakhand	534,889	359,063	10,086,292	5.3	2.53	3.56	1.7
6	Haryana	1,525,162	736,647	25,351,462	6	7.22	2.91	3.49
7	NCT of Delhi	2,265,490	769,825	16,787,941	13.5	10.73	4.59	3.65
8	Rajasthan	984,731	1,349,744	68,548,437	1.43	4.66	1.97	6.39
9	Uttar Pradesh	1,420,883	4,855,291	199,812,341	0.71	6.73	2.43	23
10	Bihar	328,290	3,054,463	104,099,452	0.31	1.55	2.93	14.47
11	Sikkim	30,831	10,254	610,577	5.05	0.15	1.68	0.05
12	Arunachal Pradesh	62,580	21,021	1,383,727	4.52	0.3	1.52	0.1
13	Nagaland	50,561	22,598	1,978,502	2.56	0.24	1.14	0.11
14	Manipur	6,848	40,920	2,855,794	0.24	0.03	1.43	0.19
15	Mizoram	20,462	8,450	1,097,206	1.86	0.1	0.77	0.04
16	Tripura	39,860	28,639	3,673,917	1.08	0.19	0.78	0.13
17	Meghalaya	42,733	28,605	2,966,889	1.54	0.22	0.96	0.13
18	Assam	142,273	291,946	31,205,576	0.46	0.67	0.94	1.38
19	West Bengal	688,515	979,049	91,276,115	0.75	3.26	0.32	4.64
20	Jharkhand	661,056	667,949	32,988,134	2	3.13	2.02	3.16
21	Odisha	310,647	594,711	41,974,218	0.74	1.47	1.42	2.87
22	Chhattisgarh	475,603	292,608	25,545,198	1.86	2.25	1.15	1.38
23	Madhya Pradesh	905,828	1,174,288	72,626,809	1.25	4.29	1.62	5.56
24	Gujarat	1,914,679	539,543	60,439,692	3.17	9.07	0.89	2.55
25	Daman and Diu	95,718	7,159	243,247	39.2	0.45	2.94	0.03
26	D & N Haveli	91,316	6,597	343,709	26.57	0.43	1.92	0.03
27	Maharashtra	3,648,355	1,206,490	112,374,333	3.25	17.28	1.07	5.71
28	Andhra Pradesh	611,057	827,308	84,580,777	0.72	2.89	0.98	3.92
29	Karnataka	1,476,200	920,725	61,095,297	2.42	6.99	1.51	4.36
30	Goa	135,456	40,755	1,458,545	9.29	0.64	2.79	0.19
31	Lakshadweep	4,623	3,211	64,473	7.17	0.02	4.98	0.01
32	Kerala	312,841	497,972	33,406,061	0.94	1.48	1.49	2.36
33	Tamil Nadu	668,488	741,732	72,147,030	0.93	3.18	1.02	3.51
34	Puducherry	125,281	108,043	1,247,953	10.04	0.59	8.66	0.51
35	A & N islands	27,064	11,711	380,551	7.11	0.13	3.08	0.05
36	Total	21,113,870	21,113,870	1,210,854,947	1.74	100	1.74	100

Source: Calculated by Author using census data 2011.

Out-migration:

Table 1, 2 and 3 represents the state wise rate and share of total and sex wise out-migration from states to other states in India between 2001 & 2011. Maximum share of total out-migrants belongs to the states having larger geographical area i.e. Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh and West Bengal etc. Almost 60 percent of the total out-migrants are migrated from above discussed 6 states of India because these states have the maximum share of poor population struggling with the problem of unemployment and peoples migrated from these states to another states in search of employment. The northern and northern eastern states i.e. Jammu & Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Mizoram, Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Nagaland, Assam, Sikkim and Tripura etc. having hilly geographical area contributed very less share in total out-migration. In states, Uttar Pradesh is the state from where maximum out-migrants are migrated and the Mizoram is the state from where very least number of peoples are out-migrated whereas from all union territories just 5 percent peoples are migrated in other states or areas. BIMARU states and some other states viz. Assam, Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Goa and Karnataka have the higher rate of out-migration in respect of their population. Half of the total male out-migrants are migrated from BIMARU states viz. Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh. Some other states like Assam Maharashtra, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Odisha, Uttarakhand and Haryana experiencing average share of out-migration. All Union territories excepting Delhi experiencing very less share of male out-migration. All of the Union Territories experience higher rate of female out-migration than the national average. There are 16 states which experience lower rate of female out-migration than the national average. Chandigarh and Puducherry are the Union territories which experience massive female out-migration in comparison of other states and Union Territories. In states, Haryana is the single state having higher rate of female out-migration among all states. More than 60 percent of females migrated in seven states only viz. Maharashtra, Gujarat, NCT of Delhi, Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana and Rajasthan and the same pattern seems in female out-migration from the states but the BIMARU states dominates here, more than 45 % female out-migrated from the BIMARU states and some other major contributed states are Haryana, Assam, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Jharkhand, NCT of Delhi and Tamil Nadu. In seven sister states located in North-East of India females from Assam migrated out of the state otherwise other 6 states contributed less than 1 percent share of total female out-migration.

Table 2: Rate and share of In-migration and Out-migration among males in India between 2001 and 2011.

Sr. No.	States	Total in-migrants from other states	Total Out-migrants to other states	Total Population	Rate of In-migration	Share of total In-migrants	Rate of Out-migration	Share of total Out-migrants
1	Jammu & Kashmir	70,628	118,532	12,541,302	0.57	0.33	0.95	0.56
2	Himachal Pradesh	205,896	171,783	6,864,602	3	0.98	1.8	2.37
3	Punjab	986,509	500,897	27,743,338	3.56	4.67	2.5	0.81
4	Chandigarh	242,517	125,341	1,055,450	22.98	1.15	11.88	0.59
5	Uttarakhand	534,889	359,063	10,086,292	5.3	2.53	3.56	1.7
6	Haryana	1,525,162	736,647	25,351,462	6	7.22	2.91	3.49
7	NCT of Delhi	2,265,490	769,825	16,787,941	13.5	10.73	4.59	3.65
8	Rajasthan	984,731	1,349,744	68,548,437	1.43	4.66	1.97	6.39
9	Uttar Pradesh	1,420,883	4,855,291	199,812,341	0.71	6.73	2.43	23
10	Bihar	328,290	3,054,463	104,099,452	0.31	1.55	2.93	14.47
11	Sikkim	30,831	10,254	610,577	5.05	0.15	1.68	0.05
12	Arunachal Pradesh	62,580	21,021	1,383,727	4.52	0.3	1.52	0.1
13	Nagaland	50,561	22,598	1,978,502	2.56	0.24	1.14	0.11
14	Manipur	6,848	40,920	2,855,794	0.24	0.03	1.43	0.19
15	Mizoram	20,462	8,450	1,097,206	1.86	0.1	0.77	0.04
16	Tripura	39,860	28,639	3,673,917	1.08	0.19	0.78	0.13
17	Meghalaya	42,733	28,605	2,966,889	1.54	0.22	0.96	0.13
18	Assam	142,273	291,946	31,205,576	0.46	0.67	0.94	1.38
19	West Bengal	688,515	979,049	91,276,115	0.75	3.26	0.32	4.64
20	Jharkhand	661,056	667,949	32,988,134	2	3.13	2.02	3.16
21	Odisha	310,647	594,711	41,974,218	0.74	1.47	1.42	2.87
22	Chhattisgarh	475,603	292,608	25,545,198	1.86	2.25	1.15	1.38
23	Madhya Pradesh	905,828	1,174,288	72,626,809	1.25	4.29	1.62	5.56
24	Gujarat	1,914,679	539,543	60,439,692	3.17	9.07	0.89	2.55
25	Daman and Diu	95,718	7,159	243,247	39.2	0.45	2.94	0.03
26	D & N Haveli	91,316	6,597	343,709	26.57	0.43	1.92	0.03
27	Maharashtra	3,648,355	1,206,490	112,374,333	3.25	17.28	1.07	5.71
28	Andhra Pradesh	611,057	827,308	84,580,777	0.72	2.89	0.98	3.92
29	Karnataka	1,476,200	920,725	61,095,297	2.42	6.99	1.51	4.36
30	Goa	135,456	40,755	1,458,545	9.29	0.64	2.79	0.19
31	Lakshadweep	4,623	3,211	64,473	7.17	0.02	4.98	0.01
32	Kerala	312,841	497,972	33,406,061	0.94	1.48	1.49	2.36
33	Tamil Nadu	668,488	741,732	72,147,030	0.93	3.18	1.02	3.51
34	Puducherry	125,281	108,043	1,247,953	10.04	0.59	8.66	0.51
35	A & N islands	27,064	11,711	380,551	7.11	0.13	3.08	0.05
36	Total	21,113,870	21,113,870	1,210,854,947	1.74	100	1.74	100

Source: Calculated by Author using census data 2011.

Table 3: Rate and share of In-migration and Out-migration among females in India between 2001 and 2011.

Sr. No.	States	Total Female In-migrants from other states	Total Female Out-migrants to other states	Total Female Population	Rate of Female In-migration	Share of Female In-migrants	Rate of Female Out-migrants	Share of Female Out-migrants
1	Jammu & Kashmir	38,249	58,952	5,900,640	0.65	0.35	1	0.53
2	Himachal Pradesh	93,553	97,845	3,382,729	2.77	0.85	2.89	0.88
3	Punjab	511,635	312,477	13,103,873	3.91	4.63	2.39	2.82
4	Chandigarh	116,225	64,648	474,787	24.48	1.05	13.62	0.58
5	Uttarakhand	278,202	210,726	4,948,519	5.62	2.51	4.26	1.9
6	Haryana	866,146	486,371	7,800,615	11.1	7.82	6.24	4.39
7	NCT of Delhi	1,110,659	427,361	11,856,728	9.37	10.03	3.6	3.86
8	Rajasthan	634,437	754,870	32,997,440	1.93	5.73	2.29	6.82
9	Uttar Pradesh	936,416	2,274,994	95,331,831	0.98	8.46	2.39	20.55
10	Bihar	261,505	1,359,205	49,821,295	0.53	2.36	2.73	12.28
11	Sikkim	13,317	5,902	287,507	4.64	0.12	2.05	0.05
12	Arunachal Pradesh	27,070	10,829	669,815	4.04	0.25	1.62	0.1
13	Nagaland	22,533	12,103	953,853	2.36	0.2	1.27	0.11
14	Manipur	3,759	20,635	1,417,208	0.27	0.03	1.46	0.19
15	Mizoram	8,432	4,410	541,867	1.56	0.08	0.81	0.04
16	Tripura	19,765	15,481	1,799,541	1.1	0.18	0.86	0.14
17	Meghalaya	23,089	16,332	1,475,057	1.57	0.21	1.11	0.15
18	Assam	79,474	507,897	15,266,133	0.52	0.72	3.33	4.59
19	West Bengal	394,559	138,018	44,467,088	0.89	3.56	0.31	1.25
20	Jharkhand	434,634	386,331	16,057,819	2.71	3.93	2.41	3.49
21	Odisha	165,796	272,598	20,762,082	0.8	1.5	1.31	2.46
22	Chhattisgarh	263,774	171,414	12,712,303	2.08	2.38	1.35	1.55
23	Madhya Pradesh	589,897	703,070	35,014,503	1.69	5.33	2.01	6.35
24	Gujarat	778,885	292,365	28,948,432	2.69	7.03	1.01	2.64
25	Daman and Diu	25,705	4,046	92,946	27.66	0.23	4.35	0.04
26	D & N Haveli	31,466	4,271	149,949	20.99	0.28	2.85	0.04
27	Maharashtra	1,613,056	700,571	54,131,277	2.98	14.57	1.29	6.33
28	Andhra Pradesh	348,120	460,473	42,138,631	0.83	3.14	1.09	4.16
29	Karnataka	733,322	542,803	30,128,640	2.44	6.62	1.8	4.9
30	Goa	61,752	22,500	719,405	8.58	0.56	3.13	0.2
31	Lakshadweep	1,181	1,654	31,350	3.77	0.01	5.28	0.02
32	Kerala	139,534	275,081	17,378,649	0.8	1.26	1.58	2.48
33	Tamil Nadu	361,500	387,901	36,009,055	1	3.27	1.08	3.5
34	Puducherry	73,011	62,262	635,442	11.49	0.66	9.8	0.56
35	A & N islands	12,246	6,508	177,710	6.89	0.11	3.66	0.06
36	Total	11,072,904	11,072,904	587,584,719	1.89	100	1.89	100

Source: Calculated by Author using census data.

Variation of In-migration and Out-migration in censuses of 2001 and 2011:-

Table 4 represents sex wise variation in In-migration and out-migration during the last two censuses. Increase in total migration between 2001 census and 2011 census is 27 percent. It is 22 percent among males and 35 percent among females.

In-migration Variation:-

In total In-migration variation there are 6 states Viz. Jammu and Kashmir, Bihar, Arunachal Pradesh, Tripura, Mizoram and West-Bengal which recorded negative growth. Andaman and Nicobar Islands is the single Union territory which recorded negative growth in total In-migration. In case of male In-migration variation, there are 7 states and 3 union territories Viz. Jammu and Kashmir, Bihar, Arunachal Pradesh, Tripura, Mizoram and West-Bengal, Assam, Chandigarh, NCT of Delhi, Andaman and Nicobar Islands which recorded negative growth. But female In-migration variation has different scenario than male In-migration variation because 4 states Viz. Jammu and Kashmir, Bihar, Arunachal Pradesh and Tripura and only one union territory named Andaman and Nicobar Islands recorded negative growth.

Table 4. Decadal growth rate of in-migration and out – migration by sex in India between 2001 and 2011

Sr. No.	States	Variation in In-migration			Variation in Out-migration		
		Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
1	Jammu & Kashmir	-18.59	-27.78	-8.76	-2.88	1.17	-6.66
2	Himachal Pradesh	9.4	4.72	15.6	3.72	-5.6	12.1
3	Punjab	21.65	7.23	39	-0.01	-7.6	5.18
4	Chandigarh	1.37	-4.17	8.18	17.49	18.19	16.85
5	Uttarakhand	51.79	46.58	56.94	1.46	-9.23	10.65
6	Haryana	23.86	14.51	32.06	25.37	21.95	27.21
7	NCT of Delhi	4.33	-5.57	17.09	68.42	72.2	65.51
8	Rajasthan	36.12	20.27	46.8	36.07	28.84	42.37
9	Uttar Pradesh	31.71	21.69	37.57	28.04	20.48	37.85
10	Bihar	-28.68	-29.57	-28.45	37.24	21.53	63.63
11	Sikkim	37.28	36.33	38.55	64.66	41.24	86.47
12	Arunachal Pradesh	-12.81	-15.28	-9.34	68.55	56.99	81.11
13	Nagaland	50.59	35.27	75.28	-56.38	-34.97	-66.07
14	Manipur	51.27	28.44	77.14	32.74	19.24	49.37
15	Mizoram	-9.45	-18.23	6.92	-73.36	-75.51	-71.03
16	Tripura	-0.99	-0.55	-1.44	21.89	10.24	33.91
17	Meghalaya	26.78	7.83	49.07	40.18	32.16	46.88
18	Assam	16.82	-2	37.74	3.94	274.19	227.76
19	West Bengal	-4.95	-18.97	9.11	34.69	-59.89	-59.76
20	Jharkhand	31.49	12.56	44.11	8.82	-2.53	18.94
21	Odisha	35.29	39.35	31.93	36.29	27.66	48.14
22	Chhattisgarh	40.4	37.7	42.65	-34.07	-39.74	-29.37
23	Madhya Pradesh	11.2	0.4	18	39.74	36.4	42.07
24	Gujarat	70.91	64.65	80.94	24.96	27.69	22.75
25	Daman and Diu	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
26	D & N Haveli	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
27	Maharashtra	12.96	5.91	23.32	37.54	33.03	40.99
28	Andhra Pradesh	45.15	43.3	46.57	31.74	27.39	35.42
29	Karnataka	68.24	68.94	67.53	20.12	9.94	28.39
30	Goa	12.29	10.08	15.05	26.27	25.63	26.8
31	Lakshadweep	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
32	Kerala	35.52	39.01	31.44	18.2	5.91	30.47
33	Tamil Nadu	174.66	164.16	184.25	25.81	16.03	36.28
34	Puducherry	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	A & N islands	-8.07	-10.57	-4.86	49.07	45.37	52.16
36	Total	27.37	22.43	35.01	27.37	22.43	35.01

Source: Calculated by Author using census data 2001 and 2011.

Out-migration variation:-

Total 4 states and 1 union territory namely Jammu and Kashmir, Punjab, Nagaland, Mizoram and Andaman and Nicobar Islands recorded negative growth in total out-migration between the censuses of 2001 and 2011. In case of male out-migration 8 states namely Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Uttarakhand, Nagaland, Mizoram, Tripura, Jharkhand and West Bengal recorded negative growth but in female out-migration only 5 states recorded negative growth rate namely Jammu and Kashmir, Nagaland, Mizoram, Chhattisgarh, and West Bengal etc.

Conclusion:-

Areas with urban and administrative centers and business developing cities attract peoples from backward and undeveloped or less developed areas where employment opportunities are very less and low life standard is present. Maharashtra, Gujrat, NCT of Delhi and Haryana are the major states which attracted a larger share of migrants which comes from various states of India. On the other hand, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar are the two

important states from where maximum number of peoples has migrated in other states in search of living. Similar pattern seems in cases of male and female in-migration and out-migration. In the census of 2011, results are similar to census of 2001 in the perspective of migration. Some of the developed states like Gujarat, Maharashtra, NCT of Delhi, Karnataka, Haryana and Punjab have both In-migration and Out-migration significantly. Development in states may be responsible for both In-migration and Out-migration. Total migration variation among 2001-2011 census periods is positively 27 percent increasing and in case of male migration it is 22 percent and in female migration it is 35 percent positively increasing. 13 states experienced domination of out-migration over in-migration and 15 states and all 7 union territories experienced domination of In-migration. In 2001, there was domination of male migration but in 2011, the picture is opposite and female migration is dominated.

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